

Endless Fun

By the Experimental Quantum Optics Group, Tampere University, Finland

The Idea of the game

Build your own high-dimensional quantum computer. By applying quantum logic operations to high-dimensional quantum bits – so-called *qudits* -, you can change their values. Try to reach the highest possible value on your qudit, while keeping the other player's qudit as low as possible. The evaluation software calculates the final state after each round, in which a certain number of measurements will project possible complex superposition states into a final value. The player with the highest qudit values summed up from all three rounds wins the game.

What you will need

- 1-7 players
- 55 Cards (You can find the exact number of the different cards in the "Cards" section of this manual)
- As many pawns as players
- 1 die
- Paper and pen to write down the points
- The evaluation software

Setup

- The players agree on which version to play:
 - **Easy version:** This is an easy method to get started. It is played in 2d, i.e. qubit values of 0 and 1 are possible, and without the phase properties. Take the following cards out of the card deck: Z, Y, H2, H3.
 - **2D version:** Qubit values of 0 and 1 are possible. In 2d, qubit values of 0 and 1 are possible. The 2d version adds cards that change the phase of single states which can control quantum interference. The H3 cards are removed from the card deck.
 - **3D version:** The qudit values can be 0, 1 and 2. All cards are used.
- Every player gets a pawn and 7 random cards, which the players hide from each other.
- Decide on a starting player by throwing a dice. The player with the highest number starts.
- The starting player is the first to choose his or her qudit position. The player marks the qudit's position by placing his or her pawn.
- Then, the other players take turns placing their pawns (in clockwise direction from starting player). The players can place their pawns only on positions neighboring already set pawns.

The layout at the start of a 4-player game after the starting positions are decided.

Playing the game

1st Round:

- The starting qudit value for all players is 0.
- The starting player starts the round by playing one card from his or her hand.
- Going clockwise, the other players take turn in playing their operations.
- The round is finished after every player has played three cards.
- Then, the played quantum operations are entered into the evaluation software to determine the winning state.
- The players earn as many points as the value of their qudit in the round's winning state. Write the points down on a paper.

2nd Round:

Round 2 is played as the previous round with the following changes:

- The starting state of all players is their winning value of the last round.
- The starting player is the player to the left side of the previous starting player.
- Every player plays only 2 cards.

3rd Round:

Round 3 is played as the previous round with the following changes:

- Only 1 card is played per player.

End of the game:

- The player with the most points summed up over all three rounds wins the game.

Cooperative mode

The cooperative mode is a game mode in which the focus is not set on individual achievement, as it is in the main game mode. In this mode, the same rules apply as in the main competitive mode. However, the goal is not to win against the other players but to reach the highest possible values summed up over all qudits as a group. The players are not allowed to show their cards to the other players and cannot discuss strategies.

Single-player mode

In the single-player mode, players can solve riddles given in the additional material of the game. The instructions for each riddle are given on the riddle cards. Therefore, the regular setup and gameplay of the multi-player mode do not apply in this mode, but the rules on how to play cards and enter the operations in the evaluation software must be followed. The solutions along with some background information can be found on the back of the cards. The players can use the evaluation software for help.

How to play cards

There are three different types of quantum operations. For all quantum operations the cards must be placed on the highest possible position beneath a qudit, but spaces to the left or right are allowed. Take a look at the truth tables at the end of the instructions to learn how they act.

Note:

- The players can put the card on any position, i.e. also apply logic operations on qudits of other players.
- The way a computation on this quantum computer works: every unitary is applied from left to right sequentially and top to bottom

1. Single qudit operations

Single qudit cards act only on one qudit and are placed beneath the qudit on which they should act on.

The cards:

4x	I	Identity operation. It does nothing.
4x	X	X_1 and X_2 operation in 3d; X operation in 2d
4x	Y	Y_1 and Y_2 operation in 3d; Y operation in 2d
4x	Z	Z_1 and Z_2 operation in 3d; Z operation in 2d
15x	Hadamard	H_1 , H_2 and H_3 operation in 3d; H_1 and H_2 operation in 2d

A possible way to place cards and the respective evaluation in 2d could be:

It is not allowed to leave empty spaces beneath a qudit.

2. Two qudit operations

These cards act on two quantum states. The quantum operations can only be played on neighboring qudits. Tilting the card signifies on which neighboring state the quantum operation acts on.

The cards:

- | | | |
|----|------|---|
| 9x | CX | CX operation. The chosen control and target are placed next to each other on the field. The card is placed on the control qudit and tilted to the target qudit. In the software a CX with control on the left and target on the right is entered as CXr (and vice versa). |
| 8x | Swap | Swaps the state with the chosen neighboring state. A tilt of the card signifies which states are swapped. In the software, swapping a state with the neighboring state on the right is entered as SWAPr (and vice versa). |

Here, the state of player 1 acts as the control and the state of player 2 as the target of the CX gate.

The swap card is tilted into the direction of the state, with which the qudit states should be swapped.

3. Other cards

The cards:

- 2x Steal Draw a random card from someone else and play it immediately.
- 5x Cancel Cancel the operation of any card already played. They subsequently turn into identities.

The cancel card is placed on top of the card that should be nullified. It is then entered as an identity operation in the software.

The evaluation software

- Run the evaluation application. Running the software in python is more powerful.
- Choose if you want to play in the easy version, in 2d, or 3d by clicking on the buttons in the top right.
- Input the starting state
 - In 2d qubit values of 0 and 1 are allowed. In 3d the possible qudit values are 0, 1 and 2.
- Input the played quantum logic gates, by clicking on the buttons in the right panel.
 - Remember that the quantum computer applies the operations sequentially from left to right and top to bottom. The gates must also be entered in that order.
 - Use the identity operation as a placeholder for empty spaces.
- Define the number of measurements or use the default value of 100.
- Click the 'Measure'-button to compute the winning state. The winning state is shown in the winning state text field, which is highlighted in yellow once the state is calculated.
 - If the Measure button is not enabled, some inputs are incorrect. Click the reset button next to it and enter the parameters again.
 - The winning state is the state, which was statistically measured the most often in the measurements.
- Click on the 'Reset'-button to evaluate the next round.

Note:

- The more measurements, the smaller the deviation of the outcome from the theoretical probability is, i.e. less luck is involved. In other words: one measurement leads to a pretty random result.
- The complete state is displayed at the bottom. It is the quantum state before its projection onto a single state through a measurement.

A first round played with 4 players in 3d in which player 1 starts with a qudit value of 0, player 2 with 2, player 3 with 1 and player 4 with 0 could for example be:

The image shows a quantum game interface for 'Endless Fun'. On the left, four players are listed with their starting qudit values and cards: Player 1 (0) has a Swap card; Player 2 (2) has a Cx card; Player 3 (1) has a Cx card; Player 4 (0) has a Cx card. On the right, the game interface shows the starting state '0210', quantum operations 'SWAPy X1 I H3', 'Z2 I I CXl', and 'I I I Y1'. The winning state is '2111'. The complete end state is displayed as a mathematical expression: $\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \exp(i \cdot 0\pi) |2122\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \exp(i \cdot \pi/3) |2111\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \exp(i \cdot 2\pi/3) |2100\rangle$.

Since the winning state is 2111, player 1 earns 2 and the other players 1 point in this round.

Truth tables of the quantum gates

Identity				
3D	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow 1\rangle$ $ 2\rangle \rightarrow 2\rangle$	3D	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow 1\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow 2\rangle$ $ 2\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle$	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow 2\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle$ $ 2\rangle \rightarrow 1\rangle$
2D	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow 1\rangle$	2D	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow 1\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle$	

Y-gate							
3D	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow e^{i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 1\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 2\rangle$ $ 2\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle$		$ 0\rangle \rightarrow e^{i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 2\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle$ $ 2\rangle \rightarrow e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 1\rangle$		3D	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow e^{i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 1\rangle$ $ 2\rangle \rightarrow e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 2\rangle$	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 1\rangle$ $ 2\rangle \rightarrow e^{i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 2\rangle$
2D	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow i 1\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow i 0\rangle$				2D	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow - 1\rangle$	

H-gate Hadamard			
3D	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} (0\rangle + e^{i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 1\rangle + e^{i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 2\rangle)$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} (0\rangle + e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 1\rangle + 2\rangle)$ $ 2\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} (0\rangle + 1\rangle + e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 2\rangle)$	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} (0\rangle + e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 1\rangle + e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 2\rangle)$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} (0\rangle + 1\rangle + e^{i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 2\rangle)$ $ 2\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} (0\rangle + e^{i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 1\rangle + 2\rangle)$	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} (0\rangle + 1\rangle + 2\rangle)$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} (0\rangle + e^{i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 1\rangle + e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 2\rangle)$ $ 2\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} (0\rangle + e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 1\rangle + e^{i\frac{2\pi}{3}} 2\rangle)$
2D	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle + 1\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle - 1\rangle$	$ 0\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle + i 1\rangle$ $ 1\rangle \rightarrow 0\rangle - i 1\rangle$	

CX

3D

$|0\rangle|0\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle|0\rangle$
 $|0\rangle|1\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle|1\rangle$
 $|0\rangle|2\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle|2\rangle$
 $|1\rangle|0\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle|1\rangle$
 $|1\rangle|1\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle|2\rangle$
 $|1\rangle|2\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle|0\rangle$
 $|2\rangle|0\rangle \rightarrow |2\rangle|2\rangle$
 $|2\rangle|1\rangle \rightarrow |2\rangle|0\rangle$
 $|2\rangle|2\rangle \rightarrow |2\rangle|1\rangle$

2D

$|0\rangle|0\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle|0\rangle$
 $|0\rangle|1\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle|1\rangle$
 $|1\rangle|0\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle|1\rangle$
 $|1\rangle|1\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle|0\rangle$

SWAP

3D

$|0\rangle|0\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle|0\rangle$
 $|0\rangle|1\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle|0\rangle$
 $|0\rangle|2\rangle \rightarrow |2\rangle|0\rangle$
 $|1\rangle|0\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle|1\rangle$
 $|1\rangle|1\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle|1\rangle$
 $|1\rangle|2\rangle \rightarrow |2\rangle|1\rangle$
 $|2\rangle|0\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle|2\rangle$
 $|2\rangle|1\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle|2\rangle$
 $|2\rangle|2\rangle \rightarrow |2\rangle|2\rangle$

2D

$|0\rangle|0\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle|0\rangle$
 $|0\rangle|1\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle|0\rangle$
 $|1\rangle|0\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle|1\rangle$
 $|1\rangle|1\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle|1\rangle$

Credits

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NOTE: The general idea is strongly based on the great card game *Q|Cards* by Oskari Kerppo, Jorden Senior, Sabrina Maniscallo, Guillermo Garcia-Perez, Samuli Jääskeläinen, Sylvia Smatanova, Krista Erkkilä, Elie Abraham, which is a very similar game using only qubits. It can be downloaded here: <https://zhamul.itch.io/qcards>

